

LORAWAN RANGE ESTIMATION BY LARGE SCALE EMPIRICAL OUTDOOR PROPAGATION MODELS

João Pedro A. Rodrigues, Walter A. Varella, Alexandre M. de Oliveira, Arnaldo de Carvalho Jr.
 IFSP (Instituto Federal, de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia de São Paulo) –
 rodrigues.joaol@aluno.ifsp.edu.br, varella@ifsp.edu.br, amanicoba@ifsp.edu.br,
 adecarvalhojr@ifsp.edu.br.

Abstract – LoRaWAN is receiving significant attention for internet of things (IoT) projects because it is low-power, low-data rate over a wide range coverage area. Range estimation is an important process of any radio network planning, including LoRaWAN. This paper presents a study comparing LoRaWAN estimation based on 3 empirical propagation models, Free Space Loss, Egli and Okumura-Hata models and LoRa devices specifications.

Keywords: LoRaWAN, IoT, Okumura-Hata, Egli, Path Loss.

INTRODUCTION

Internet of things (IoT) is an emerging topic in areas such as agriculture, transportation, logistics smart cities, smart grids, and industry 4.0 [1].

Advances in wireless technology and digital electronics have allowed small devices to be used on various IoT projects. These devices can form the wireless sensor network (WSN) for internet connection to detect and monitor IoT processes [2].

Low-cost, low-complexity and low-power operations are desirable features for WSN devices. Starting 2015, long range (LoRa) wide area networks (LoRaWAN) protocols has been gaining attention from researchers by meeting these questions [3].

LoRa physical layer has been patented by Semtech in 2014. LoRa uses and adaption of chirp spread spectrum (CSS) modulation, making it robust against disturbances and allowing it to be received across large distances [3].

LoRaWAN is a media access control layer (MAC) protocol that allows us to create a network of WSN devices connected to a gateway in a coverage cells way, similar to a mobile communication network [3], as showed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – LoraWAN topology.
 Source: Adapted of [4]

The path loss (PL) prediction helps radio engineers to understand the environmental effects on the electromagnetic (EM) waves. PL is an important tool for planning and optimizing the long-range network radio network (LoRaWAN), by supporting the LoRa nodes placement [5].

Empirical Propagation models can be used to predict the strength of a radio wave signal received at a given distance relative to the position of the LoRaWAN gateway [5]. This allow us to estimate the

maximum distance between the sensor node and the gateway.

Here, we will use the empirical Free Space Loss, Egli and Okumura-Hata propagation models to estimate the maximum range of a LoRaWAN system, given the device specifications, environmental characteristics and frequency.

DEVELOPMENT

The maximum LoRaWAN path loss (PL) is calculated by the difference between of the effective radiated power from the transmitter side and the minimum effective received power (or receiver sensitivity) at the receiver side, as Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Path Loss concept.
 Source: Adapted of [6].

PL can be calculated as Equation 1 [7],[8].

$$PL = P_{TX} - L_{TX} + G_{ATX} - M + G_{ARX} - L_{RX} - Rx_{sens} \quad (1)$$

Where PL is the path loss, P_{TX} is the transmitter power (dBm), L_{TX} and L_{RX} are the insertion and cable losses from transmitter and receiver, G_{ATX} and G_{ARX} are the transmitter and receiver antenna gain, M is the noise margin and Rx_{sens} is the receiver sensitivity. Since LoRaWAN is a duplex system, the PL must be calculated in both directions. The smallest path loss will be the limiting link PL for the range estimation, downlink (DL) or uplink (UL). LoRa Rx_{sens} depends on the data rate and SF used. It is given by Equations 2 and 3 [9].

$$SNR = (SF - 7) * (-2.5) - 7.5 \quad (2)$$

$$Rx_{sens} = -174 + 10 \log(BW) + NF + SNR \quad (3)$$

Where SNR is the signal to noise ratio (dB), NF is the noise figure of the LoRa radio devices (dB),

BW is the bandwidth (from 7.8 to 500 kHz) and SF is the spreading factor used for the LoRa project.

The simplest propagation model to estimate the range of the link is the free space loss (FSL) model. It is based on the Friis formula and consider directly view without any obstructions between transmitter and receiver. The distance D can be calculated as Equation 4 [10].

$$D=10^{(PL-32.44-20\log(F)/20)} \quad (4)$$

Where D is the distance in km, and F is the frequency of LoRa in MHz.

Egli is a terrain model, first introduced by John Egli in 1957, based on real-world measurements in VHF and UHF bands for television transmission in several large cities of the USA. It is typically used for outdoor over irregular terrain [11]. The range of the LoRa link can be calculated based on Egli's model as Equation 5.

$$D=10^{(PL-X-20\log(F)+20\log(H_{TX})+10\log(H_{RX})/40)} \quad (5)$$

Where D is the distance in km, F is the frequency in MHz, H_{TX} and H_{RX} are the transmitter and receiver antenna heights in meters and X is a constant 76.3 if H_{RX} is lower or equal to 10 m and 85.9 for higher H_{RX} values.

The Okumura-Hata model is an empirical radio propagation model developed in two steps. First Okumura collected VHF and UHF data measurements from the city of Tokyo/Japan in 1968 and presented the results in a collection of curves. Later, in 1980, Hata used Okumura results to develop equations that bring some of these curves closer. The equations package is known as Okumura-Hata model. The model is used as a reference for mobile networks in different urban scenarios [11],[12]. The model consider different morphology structures as well as a correction factor based on the receiver height. Equation 6-9 presents the basic Okumura-Hata model. The parameters dependent on morphology and receiver antenna heights are in Equations 10-12.

$$D=10^{((PL-A-C)/B)} \quad (6)$$

$$A=69.55+26.16\log(F)-13.82\log(H_{TX}-a) \quad (7)$$

$$B=44.9-6.55\log(H_{TX}) \quad (8)$$

For rural and open areas:

$$C=-4.78(\log(F))^2+18.33\log(F)-40.98 \quad (9)$$

$$a=(1.1\log(F)-0.7)H_{RX}-(1.56\log(F)-0.8) \quad (10)$$

For suburban areas:

$$C=2(\log(F/28))^2-5.4 \quad (11)$$

a is calculated as rural and open areas.

For medium cities:

$C=0$ and a is calculated as rural and open areas.

For large cities:

$$a=3.2(\log(11.75H_{RX}))^2-4.97 \quad (12)$$

Where F is in MHz, D is in km, H_{TX} and H_{RX} are in meters.

In this study we programmed an algorithm using the open source Scilab math software and made available at [13].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The algorithm starts cleaning the Scilab memory and console. After that the software starts to ask all the input values of the LoRa devices, environment and link characteristics. Figure 3 presents one example.

```
Scilab 2024.1.0 Console
*** LORAWAN RANGE ESTIMATION ***
Enter the central frequency (in MHz): 917

Enter the Morphology (1-Open/Rural Area, 2-Suburban, 3-Median City, 4-Large City): 2

Data from the LoRaWAN Gateway
Enter the Gateway Antenna Height (in meters): 10

Enter the Gateway Antenna Gain (in dBi): 2

Enter the Cable and Insertion Losses (in dB): 0

Enter the Gateway Transmitter Power (in dBm): 10

Data from LoRa Sensor Node
Enter the Node Antenna Height (in meters): 1

Enter the Node Antenna Gain (in dBi): 2

Enter the Cable and Insertion Losses (in dB): 0

Enter the Sensor Node Transmitter Power (in dBm): 0

Communication Data
Enter the Bandwidth (in kHz): 12.5

Enter the Spreading Factor (SF) (7 to 12): 12

Enter the Noise Figure (NF) for the LoRa devices (in dB): 0

Enter the Noise and Losses Margins (in dB): 5
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Figure 3 – Inputs for the LoRaWAN Estimator.
Source: The Author (2024).

After that the algorithm executes the calculation, ask the user to clean the console and present the results of the range estimator in meters, as the Figure 4. At the end the program ask if the user wants to run the calculation again.

```
Scilab 2024.1.0 Console
*** LORAWAN SYSTM RANGE ESTIMATION ***
Free Space Range Estimation (meters): 130971.16

Range Estimation by Egli Propagation Model (meters): 2897.93
Range Estimation from Okumura-Hata Propagation Model (meters): 1593.42

Wants another study (Y/N) ?
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Figure 4 – Outputs for the LoRaWAN Estimator.
Source: The Author (2024).

Considering the parameters in Table 1 and Table 2, the results are presented in Table 3.

By just changing the SF 7 to SF 12 in the Table 1, meaning that the data-rate changes from 5.47 kilo bits per second (kbps) to just 293 bps, the new range estimation results is presented on TABLE 4.

TABLE 1 – LoRa Device Values.

Parameter	Value
LoRa transceiver NF	6 dB
Transmitter Power	10 dBm
Antenna Gain	2 dBi
Bandwidth	125 kHz
SF	7

TABLE 2 – Environment Parameters.

Parameter	Value
Gateway Antenna Height	15 m
Sensor Node Antenna Height	1 m
Insertion and Cable Losses	0 dB
Morpho	Rural
Frequency	917 MHz
Margin	6 B

TABLE 3 – LoRa Range Estimation Results for SF 7.

Propagation Model	Range Estimation
Free Space Loss	123,644.74 m
Egli	3,448.53 m
Okumura-Hata	5,775.48 m

TABLE 4 – LoRa Range Estimation Results for SF 12.

Propagation Model	Range Estimation
Free Space Loss	464,703.19 m
Egli	6,685.49 m
Okumura-Hata	11,769.44 m

The SF, and the data-rate, has a significant effect on the LoRa range. Comparing Table 3 and Table 4 we see that the range estimation is almost 4x considering FSL and 2x considering Egli or Okumura-Hata propagation models.

Penetration losses can also be added on the margin value to evaluate the impact of some obstruction loss near the sensor nodes in the range estimation [15],[16],[17].

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this project has been achieved and an easy-to-use algorithm has been elaborated, capable of estimating the range of a LoRaWAN system.

By introducing data from the device specs, project and the environment, the software provides the estimated range using 3 propagation models: FSL, Egli and Okumura-Hata. The first is naturally optimistic and can be used for links without obstruction. The second and third models depends on the morphology used. The Okumura-Hata model is more optimistic than Egli in scenarios of open and rural areas. On the other hand, Egli is more optimistic in urban environments than Okumura-Hata. The FSL model can be unreal, especially for ranges longer than the allowed by the Earth curvature.

The tool presented in this article can be useful to simulate the impact of choosing BW and SF from the LoRa system. The tool also can be used to evaluate the performance of devices with different NF. Obstructions can be considered in the study by adding losses to the Margin value.

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